

BASIC TECHNOLOGIES OF GAS THERMAL SPRAYING COATINGS

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Abstract This article provides information about the essence of gas-thermal coating processes, the formation of a directed flow of dispersed particles of material, their transfer to the surface of the workpiece and the formation of a coating layer.

Key Words: material, increased ductility, adhesive ability, high temperature.

The essence of gas-thermal coating processes is the formation of a directed flow of dispersed particles of the sprayed material, ensuring their transfer to the surface of the workpiece and the formation of a coating layer.

The coating is created due to adhesion that occurs when particles collide on the surface of the base. Sprayed particles can be a powder or can be obtained by melting and gas crushing of the starting material - wire, rods, plasticized mass, etc. Various high-temperature gaseous media are used to accelerate the particles. Heating of the sprayed material is carried out to increase the plasticity and adhesive ability of the particles. Gas-thermal coatings, like surfacing coatings, are applied to protect the surface from wear and high temperature, and are also widely used to restore the geometry of a product that has been damaged (during production or operation). There is no uniform classification of thermal spraying methods. According to the GOST 28076–89 standard, gas-thermal coatings are divided into classes according to their functional purpose and energy characteristics, since the fundamental difference between gas-thermal spraying technologies is determined by the type of energy source. Most thermal spraying methods are universal, as they allow the application of a wide range of materials. Materials for spraying, in turn, can have different shapes (powders, wire, rods). Therefore, the classification of thermal

spraying technologies can be supplemented with the characteristics of the material for spraying.

The gas-flame coating method uses the heat released during the combustion of flammable gases (acetylene, propane-butane, hydrogen, methane, natural gas, etc.) mixed with oxygen or compressed air. The temperature of the combustion products of flammable gases reaches 2000–3000 °C. Acetylene-oxygen flame has the highest specific heat flux, so it is the most common. Depending on whether the combustible gas and oxidizer were or were not moved before being supplied to the combustion zone, a distinction is made between pre-moved and diffusion flames. Gas, when flowing into an unlimited space filled with air or other gas, forms a jet called a torch. The peripheral sections of the jet involve air or other gas from the environment into movement. As the driving mass increases and its speed decreases, the cross-section of the jet continuously increases and the entire jet takes on the shape of an expanding cone. The jet opening angle is approximately 25°.

The powder is fed, as a rule, along the axis of the flame, into it. The temperature when acetylene is used as a flammable gas reaches 3200 °C, and the flow velocity is 150-160 m/s. Once in the jet, the powder particles melt or become highly plastic and acquire a speed of 20–80 m/s. The flight speed of powder particles depends on the ratio of oxygen and combustible gas in the mixture, the flow rate of the blowing gas, the distance from the nozzle exit, the flow rate of the powder introduced into the flame, its density, particle size distribution and other factors. If during the gas-flame process the sprayed material has the form of a rod or wire, then it is fed by a special electromechanical drive into the central hole. In region 1, melt droplets form, which are transferred by a stream of compressed air to the surface of the workpiece. The advantages of flame spraying of coatings include: 1) the ability to obtain coatings from most materials that melt at temperatures up to 3000 °C without decomposition; 2) fairly high process productivity (up to 8-10 kg/h of self-fluxing alloy powders) with a high material utilization rate (more than 95%); 3) relatively low level of noise and light emissions, allowing the operator to work

without additional protective equipment; 77 4) ease and simplicity of maintenance, low cost and mobility of equipment, which allows spraying to be carried out on site, without dismantling the products. The main disadvantages of the gas-flame method of spraying coatings from powder materials are:

- 1) limitation of sprayed materials by melting temperature (not more than 3000 0 C);
- 2) insufficient adhesion strength of coatings to the base;
- 3) high porosity of coatings, which prevents their use in corrosive environments without additional treatment;
- 4) low coefficient of energy use of the gas-flame jet for heating the powder material (2–12%).

The plasma method is the most versatile and technologically advanced thermal spraying process. Coating involves forming on the surface of a part (product, structure) a layer of particles that have a certain supply of thermal and kinetic energy obtained as a result of interaction with a plasma jet. The temperature of the plasma jet reaches 5000–5500 0 C, and the exhaust speed is 1000–1500 m/s. In a plasma jet, particles acquire a speed of 50–200 m/s. The flight speed of particles depends on their size, material density, arc current, and the nature and flow rate of the plasma-forming gas. Plasma jets are produced in special devices called plasma generators or plasmotrons. The plasma torch consists of a water-cooled cathode, an anode and an insulator separating them. Plasma-forming gas (argon, high-purity nitrogen, helium, hydrogen, etc.) is supplied to an electric arc excited between the rod cathode and the annular anode (nozzle), is heated and flows out of the nozzle in the form of a plasma jet. The sprayed material is introduced into the plasma jet in the form of a powder or wire behind the anode spot; it is possible to enter the arc with plasma-forming gas. In plasma spraying, the powder is blown into the plasma jet by a transport gas directly through special holes in the plasma torch. Wire and rods can be fed in two ways.

The advantages of the method are: 1) the possibility of obtaining coatings from most materials that melt without decomposition, without restrictions on the melting temperature; 2) the possibility of using various types of gases to form an arc plasma jet: inert (argon, helium), reducing (hydrogen) and oxidizing (air, nitrogen), also ammonia, natural gas, water vapor, which in combination with the use of chambers with protective medium (vacuum) or protective attachments allows you to regulate the properties of the medium in which the powder particles heat up and move; 3) the possibility of flexible regulation of the electrical and gas operating modes of the plasmatron, including during the coating process, which allows you to control the energy characteristics of the sprayed particles and the conditions for coating formation; 4) fairly high process productivity: 3-20 kg/h for plasma torches with an electrical power of 30-40 kW and 50-80 kg/h for plasma torches with a power of 150-200 kW; 5) a fairly high coefficient of powder utilization (50...70%), depending mainly on the type of sprayed material. The disadvantages of the plasma-arc method of applying coatings in an open atmosphere are: 1) low adhesion strength of coatings to the substrate for a number of operating conditions; 2) high porosity of the resulting coatings, which prevents their use in corrosive environments without additional processing; 3) low efficiency factor of the plasma jet energy for heating the powder (2–8%); 4) high level of noise (110–130 dB) and radiation; 5) the relatively high cost of equipment and its stationary nature.

3.1.3. Electric arc metallization

The essence of the electrometalization process is the melting of wire with an electric arc and spraying of the molten metal with compressed air. During electric arc metallization (Fig. 3.6), voltage is applied to wires made of sprayed material 1 from a direct welding current source and an electric arc is excited. Compressed air is supplied into the arc gap through nozzle 2, which transfers the molten metal of the wire in the form of small drops to the surface of the workpiece. The product is usually located at a distance of 10–20 cm from the metallizer nozzle. Instead of compressed air, the inert gas argon is sometimes used. This avoids significant oxidation of the sprayed material and improves the quality of the coating.

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